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MOLECULAR REARRANGEMENT OF SOME *O*-ACYLOXYACETARONES IN PRESENCE OF METALLIC SODIUM

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The triacetate and the tribenzoate of phloracetophenone and the diacetates and dibenzoates of quinacetophenone, respropiofenone and resbutyrophenone have been subjected to molecular rearrangement in presence of metallic sodium in dry toluene. The acetates on molecular rearrangement gave the known chromone derivatives and the benzoates, the known flavone derivatives except in the case of resbutyrophenone dibenzoate where only benzoic acid was isolated.

Baker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1381) observed that *o*-aroyloxyacylarones could be transformed to *o*-hydroxydiaroylmethanes by means of potassium carbonate. These β -diketones could then be transformed into chromones and flavones by dehydration. A number of reagents have been found to bring about this rearrangement. Mahal and Venkataraman (*ibid.*, 1934, 1767) found sodamide to be effective. Virkar and Wheeler (*ibid.*, 1939, 1679) observed that metallic sodium in dry toluene or dry ether could bring about the same rearrangement. They also found that by using metallic sodium molecular rearrangement of resacetophenone diacetate and 4-*O*-benzoyl-2-*O*-acetylresacetophenone, which could not be carried out by the use of potassium carbonate, could be effected and that it provided a convenient process for the synthesis of 2-naphthylchromones, nitroflavones and 2-alkylchromones. Virkar (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1942, 11, III, 136) and Virkar and Shah (*ibid.*, 1942, 11, III, 140; *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 30A, 57) have subjected a number of *o*-acyloxyacetoarones to this rearrangement in presence of metallic sodium. Ullal, Shah and Wheeler (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1499) found that alcoholic sodium ethoxide also brought about the same rearrangement at room temperature.

Though a large number of *o*-acyloxyacetoarones have been subjected to molecular rearrangement, the acetates and benzoates of the two simple ketones, quinacetophenone and phloracetophenone, have not been subjected to this rearrangement. Further, the work done so far has been restricted to *o*-acyloxyacetoarones and no work has been carried out on the *o*-acyloxypropiofenones and *o*-acyloxybutyrofenones. The triacetate and the tribenzoate of phloracetophenone and the diacetates and dibenzoates of quinacetophenone, respropiofenone and resbutyrophenone have therefore been subjected to this molecular rearrangement in presence of metallic sodium, as this reagent has been found by Virkar *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) to give the best results.

Phloracetophenone triacetate and tribenzoate on molecular rearrangement gave the known 5:7-dihydroxy-3-acetyl-2-methylchromone and 5:7-dihydroxy-3-benzoylflavone respectively. Quinacetophenone diacetate and dibenzoate gave the known 6-hydroxy-3-acetyl-2-methylchromone and 6-hydroxyflavone respectively. Respropiofenone diacetate and dibenzoate gave the known 7-hydroxy-2:3-dimethylchromone and 7-hydroxy-3-methylflavone respectively and resbutyrophenone diacetate gave the known 7-hydroxy-2-methyl-3-ethylchromone. In the case of resbutyrophenone dibenzoate only benzoic acid could be isolated from the reaction mixture. The intermediate β -diketones could not be isolated in any of these rearrangements.

The mechanism for the formation of simple and 3-acylchromones from the *o*-acyloxyacylarones in this rearrangement is very likely the same as that given by Baker (*loc. cit.*) for the formation of chromones when an *o*-hydroxyacylarone is heated with the anhydride and the sodium salt of a fatty acid.

The work on the diacetates and the dibenzoates of respropiofenone and resbutyrophenone provides some data regarding the effect of the acyl group other than the acetyl in this rearrangement. The only other data available of this nature are the molecular rearrangements of 2-phenylacetyl-1-naphthylcinnamate and 2-phenylacetyl-1-naphthylacetate which were found to undergo transformations into 2-styryl-3-phenyl-1:4- α -naphthapyrone and 2-methyl-3-phenyl-1:4- α -naphthapyrone respectively in presence of soda-mide (Bhalla, Mahal and Venkataraman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 863).

EXPERIMENTAL

Molecular Rearrangement of Phloracetophenone Triacetate: 5:7-Dihydroxy-3-acetyl-2-methylchromone.—Phloracetophenone triacetate (6 g.), prepared according to Gulati, Seth and Venkataraman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1766), was dissolved in dry toluene (25 c.c.) and was added to pulverised sodium (0.8 g.). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hours between 120° and 130° in an oil-bath. At the end of that period the unreacted sodium was dissolved in alcohol and the reaction mixture was filtered. The residue consisting of the sodium salt was decomposed with dilute acetic acid and the 5:7-dihydroxy-3-acetyl-2-methylchromone obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol in reddish prisms (1.75 g.), m.p. 251°. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 4.1. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$: C, 61.4; H, 4.3 per cent). This was deacetylated to 5:7-dihydroxy-2-methylchromone by heating with 10% sodium carbonate solution. The product obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol in dark yellow plates, m.p. 278°. Gulati, Seth and Venkataraman (*loc. cit.*) who obtained these chromones in their work on the Kostanecki acetylation of phloracetophenone give m.p. 252° and 279° respectively for the two products.

Molecular Rearrangement of Phloracetophenone Tribenzoate: 5:7-Dihydroxy-3-benzoylflavone.—Phloracetophenone tribenzoate, prepared from phloracetophenone by the Schotten-Bauman method, was crystallised from rectified spirit in pink needles, m.p. 118°. Canter, Curd and Robertson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1248) give m.p. 117°. The tribenzoate (4 g.), dissolved in dry toluene (25 c.c.), was added to pulverised sodium (0.8 g.) and the reaction mixture was heated for 4 hours at 120°-130° in an oil-bath and the 5:7-dihydroxy-3-benzoylflavone, obtained on working up the reaction mixture as before, was crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale pink needles (2.1 g.), m.p. 143-44°. (Found: C, 68.3; H, 4.4. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$: C, 68.8; H, 4.5 per cent).

The 3-benzoylflavone was debenzoylated to 5:7-dihydroxyflavone by boiling with 10% sodium carbonate solution. The product obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol in reddish prisms, m.p. 273°. Trivedi, Sethna and Shah (*this Journal*, 1943, 20, 172) who obtained these products in their work on the Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation of phloracetophenone, give m. p. 145-46° and 275° respectively for the two compounds.

Molecular Rearrangement of Quinacetophenone Diacetate: 6-Hydroxy-3-acetyl-2-methylchromone.—Quinacetophenone, prepared according to Amin and Shah (this *Journal*, 1948, 28, 381) was converted into its diacetate by heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine. The diacetate on crystallisation from alcohol gave white needles, m.p. 68°. Klinger and Kolvenbach (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 1216) give the same m.p.

Quinacetophenone diacetate (4 g.) was heated with pulverised sodium (0.3 g.) in dry toluene (20 c.c.) for 6 hours at 120°-130°. The product obtained on working up as usual gave from absolute alcohol pale brown needles (0.92 g.), m.p. 215°. This product was directly compared with an authentic specimen of 6-hydroxy-3-acetyl-2-methylchromone, prepared by the Kostanecki acetylation of quinacetophenone according to Desai and Mavani (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1947, 26A, 354) who give m.p. 221° for this product. It was deacetylated to 6-hydroxy-2-methylchromone, m.p. 252°, by boiling with sodium carbonate solution. Desai and Mavani (*loc. cit.*) give the same m.p.

Molecular Rearrangement of Quinacetophenone Dibenzoate: 6-Hydroxyflavone.—Quinacetophenone dibenzoate was prepared by benzoylating quinacetophenone with benzoyl chloride and pyridine. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale brown needles, m.p. 113°. Klinger and Kolvenbach (*loc. cit.*) give the same m.p.

Quinacetophenone dibenzoate (4 g.) was heated with pulverised sodium (0.8 g.) in dry toluene (60 c.c.) for 4 hours at 120°-130°. On working up the reaction mixture 6-hydroxyflavone was obtained. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in light yellow prisms, m.p. 231°. (Found: C, 75.2; H, 4.6. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{10}O_2$: C, 75.6. H, 4.2 per cent). Chadha and Venkataraman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1075), who obtained it in their work on the benzoylation of quinacetophenone, give m.p. 234°. Kostanecki, Levi and Tambor (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 331) give m.p. 231-32°.

Molecular Rearrangement of Respropiophenone Diacetate: 7-Hydroxy-2:3-dimethylchromone.—Respropiophenone was prepared from resorcinol by the application of Hoesch's method according to Canter, Curd and Robertson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1262). Its hitherto unknown *diacetate* was prepared by heating respropiophenone (4 g.) with acetic anhydride (12 c.c.) and a few drops of pyridine for 4 hours. The oil obtained on pouring the reaction mixture into ice and hydrochloric acid was taken up in ether and washed with dilute alkali and water. The oil obtained on removal of ether gave no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. This was distilled under reduced pressure but the distilled product gave characteristic coloration with ferric chloride. The product, however, was almost insoluble in alkali indicating that the decomposition was slight. However, for the purposes of analysis and rearrangement the washed oil, which did not give any coloration, was dried under reduced pressure at 100° and then used. (Found: C, 62.5; H, 5.7. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 62.4; H, 5.6 per cent).

Respropiophenone diacetate (3 g.), dissolved in dry toluene (30 c.c.), was added to pulverised sodium (0.6 g.). The reaction mixture was heated for 4 hours at 120°-130°. On working up the reaction mixture 7-hydroxy-2:3-dimethylchromone was obtained which was crystallised from rectified spirit in pale green needles (0.67 g.), m.p. 262°. (Found: C, 69.6; H, 5.7. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{16}O_2$: C, 69.5; H, 5.3 per cent). Canter, Curd and Robertson (*loc. cit.*) who prepared it by the Kostanecki acetylation of respropiophenone, give m.p. 265°.

Molecular Rearrangement of Respropiophenone Dibenzoate: 7-Hydroxy-3-methylflavone.—The hitherto unknown *respropiophenone dibenzoate* was prepared from *respropiophenone* (3 g.), dissolved in pyridine and benzoyl chloride (4.5 c.c.). The reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for 3 hours and then poured in ice and hydrochloric acid. The solid separating was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water and it was crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine orange colored needles (4.5 g.), m.p. 88-89°. (Found: C, 73.9; H, 4.8. $C_{23}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 73.8; H, 4.8 per cent).

Respropiophenone dibenzoate (2 g.), dissolved in dry toluene (30 c.c.), was added to pulverised sodium (0.4 g.) and the reaction mixture heated in an oil-bath at 120°-130° for 4 hours. On working up the reaction mixture 7-hydroxy-3-methylflavone was obtained. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale cream colored plates (0.23 g.), m.p. 278°. (Found: C, 76.2; H, 4.8. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$: C, 76.2; H, 4.4 per cent). Canter, Curd and Robertson (*loc. cit.*), who prepared it by benzoylation of *respropiophenone*, give the same m.p.

Molecular Rearrangement of Resbutyrophenone Diacetate: 7-Hydroxy-3-ethyl-2-methylchromone.—*Resbutyrophenone* was prepared according to Brewster and Harris (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 4869) from *resorcinol*, *butyric acid* and *zinc chloride*. The hitherto unknown *resbutyrophenone diacetate* was prepared by refluxing *resbutyrophenone* (5 g.), *acetic anhydride* (20 c.c.) and a few drops of *pyridine*. On pouring it in ice and dilute hydrochloric acid a liquid separated which was taken up in ether. The ether extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. On removal of ether viscous liquid remained which was distilled, b.p. 170°-175°/15 mm. Slight decomposition seemed to take place during distillation as the distilled product though insoluble in alkali gave reddish coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 63.3; H, 6.6. $C_{14}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 63.6; H, 6.1 per cent).

Resbutyrophenone diacetate (4 g.), dissolved in dry toluene (30 c.c.), was added to pulverised sodium (0.8 g.) and heated for 4 hours at 120°-130°. The reaction mixture on working up as usual gave 7-hydroxy-3-ethyl-2-methylchromone which was crystallised from rectified spirit in pale greenish blue needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 238°. (Found: C, 71.1; H, 6.2. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.9 per cent). Canter, Curd and Robertson (*loc. cit.*) who prepared it by the Kostanecki acetylation of *resbutyrophenone*, give the same m.p.

Attempted Molecular Rearrangement of Resbutyrophenone Dibenzoate.—The hitherto unknown *resbutyrophenone dibenzoate* was prepared from *resbutyrophenone* (5 g.), dissolved in sufficient pyridine and benzoyl chloride (15 c.c.). The reaction mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for 3 hours. On working up the reaction mixture as usual an oily liquid separated which was distilled, b.p. 210°/25 mm. (Found: C, 74.1; H, 4.9. $C_{24}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 74.2; H, 5.2 per cent). When *resbutyrophenone dibenzoate* was subjected to molecular rearrangement under different conditions of reaction the only product which could be isolated was benzoic acid.

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